

Non-Native English-Speaking Teachers' Identity and Paradigm Shift in English Language Teaching: Current Trend in Thai Educational Context

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Abstract

English is currently the main means of international communication among people from diverse linguistic backgrounds. Therefore, English language education has played a significant role in all domains of society and connecting people globally. There has been a significant increase in the number of the controversial native/non-native dichotomy in English Language Teaching (ELT). The fallacy that successful communication can always be assured if an individual can approximate to the native speakers' competence has long been prevalent to uphold in English language education in Thailand. This paper aims to criticize the non-native English-speaking teachers' identity in accordance with the dominant native speakers' norms of English in Thailand as well as the use of English teaching paradigm which contradicts the sociolinguistic reality of today's world communication. This paper reconceptualizes the status of Non-Native English Speaking Teachers (NNESTs) through the lens of professional identity and the orientation of English language teaching pedagogy in current trend of Thai educational setting in order to raise educators and scholars' awareness of the importance of international intelligibility rather than linguistic prestige. Additionally, the English teacher identity and paradigm shift in English language teaching in Thailand will be proposed. Such issues will provide a powerful lens to reexamine the value in English language teachers in many dimensions: the requirement through qualifications, students' viewpoints and administrators' perspectives. Hopefully, the critical discussion in the paper would offer the insight into dominant teaching paradigm in Thailand which should be reconsidered to be compatible with global communicative needs, particularly in the era of international communication and ELT.

Introduction

The alternation of two languages inside and outside of sentences –codeswitching (CS hereafter) has been studied mainly from two perspectives, i.e. Grammatical/syntactic and pragmatic/discourse (Romaine, 1995; Jake, 1994). Although these two aspects are related and a knowledge of one helps understand the other (Jake & Myers-Scotton, 1997; Myers-Scotton, 2002; Hebblethwaite, 2010). A number of researchers have proposed descriptive grammatical constraints in CS, rather than theoretical. Poplack's study on Spanish/English bilinguals (1980) was one of the most influential studies. Her study is specifically based on syntactically close languages, i.e. English / Spanish, but counterexamples can be found in syntactically distant languages. In the 1980s some other models were proposed to define grammatical constraint, e.g. Chomskians' Government Binding model by Di Sciullo, Muysken and Singh (1986). Myers-Scotton and her associate Azuma developed a model based on speech production theory, i.e. Azuma's frame-content hypothesis (1993) and Myers-Scotton's Matrix Language Frame (MLF) model (1993). Myers-Scotton's MLF model is an abstract theoretical model, but it has been employed to examine contact phenomenon among a variety of languages since the 90s. Her MLF model was revised in Myers-Scotton, 1997 and extended sub-models were proposed (Jake & Myers-Scotton, 2002; Myers-Scotton & Jake, 2017; Kniáz & Zawrotna, 2020).

The concept of the MLF model is influenced by psycholinguistic theories. The most significant of the three are the differential activation of base language and guest language (Grosjean, 1988 quoted in Myers-Scotton, 1993), the different retrieval process of closed class items and open items in Garret's speech error study (1975 quoted in Myers-Scotton, 1993), and lemmas in the mental lexicon linking conceptual information and grammatical function in Levelt's language production model (1989 cited in Myers-Scotton, 1993). Urdu-English code switching is evident in health and science related data sets. Recent covid-19 pandemic has proved that certain data sets are being produced every day. Frequent use of English content words in Urdu bilingual speech helps in realizing potentials and constraints of both languages. In a single conversation, there is always a mutual understanding between the speaker and interlocutors. The speaker is in the mode of communicating while

considering semantic, pragmatic and socio-pragmatic aspects of interlocutors (Myers-Scotton 1996; Jake & Myers-Scotton, 2009). Both languages in connection have definite roles and MLF model explains these in interpretations. Myers-Scotton (1993a, 1997, p. 82) proposed System Morpheme Principle (SMP) along with Morpheme Order Principle (MOP) to present an argument on bilingual constituents of participating languages. In this argument, Matrix language (ML) provides morphosyntactic frame, whereas lexical items such as nouns and verbs are inserted from Embedded language (EL). This analysis is focused on Urdu-English data sets. These data sets were converted into their English translation and then roman Urdu version. Data is available online at the BBC Urdu website (<https://www.bbc.com/urdu/science-54677744>). The article was written to provide information about the nature of the virus and the very natural flow of the text made it highly suitable for this analysis. The lack of the “observer's paradox” (Labov, 1972, p. 79). Code mixing denotes a phenomenon where two languages are observed in a single sentence carrying lexical and grammatical features from both languages. However, there are set rules for the insertion of the items. These insertions are often unconscious, abrupt and unplanned but almost all productions seem to follow the same criteria. Muysken (2011) discusses code mixing with reference to language mixture. Urdu-English code switching can be intra-sentential or inter-sentential. CS can be structurally divided into inter-sentential CS and intra-sentential CS. The inter-sentential CS has been broadly studied in the sociolinguistic field, but grammatical constraints are not a major focus there. With the intra-sentential CS, grammatical constraints directly affect the behaviour of two, or more participating languages (Youssef, 2017). The MLF model is devised to explain intra-sentential CS as both Urdu and English are extensively used in formal education, public sector and industry. Though both languages are used in the expressions, code-switching confirms that Urdu is the only language that provides morphosyntactic frame of the clause in data sets as proposed by Myers Scotton (2005). Language production at the abstract level confirms bilingual constituents at the surface level of data sets and this is discussed in MLF principles. This data set contains Urdu-English data with an intra-sentential code switching. Clyne (2003) and Muysken (2000) both argued that the cognitive aspects in language development and processing need careful scrutiny on the part of researchers.

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